

The Leadership & Management Style of Ho Chi Minh Practical Value and Significance

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Abstract—*The leadership and management style of Ho Chi Minh is a fundamental part of his working style, playing a decisive role in the correctness of guidelines and leadership of the Ruling Party; management decisions of the State of Vietnam, creating social consensus, ensuring the Vietnamese revolution always has enough strength to overcome all difficulties and challenges in the development process. That style remains intact and is of particular importance to Vietnam in the current fierce political competition.*

Keywords— *Ho Chi Minh; style; leadership; management.*

Leadership and management are two different but closely interrelated aspects. Leadership is to set the direction and the will for everyone to follow, and the management is to make administrative orders and to control common activities. The distinction between leadership and management is the basis for overcoming the phenomenon of overlapping functions, making changes or relying on, depending on the subjects of these two activities. However, leadership and management can be carried out entirely by a subject. In other words, a subject can be both a leader and a manager.

Regarding the concept of leadership and management, there are many different understandings. There is a perception that: "Leadership is a process that affects people so that they are willing and enthusiastic to strive to achieve the goals of the organization. Leadership is instruction, control, order and advance" [1]. Or, "Leadership is a process that affects the activities of an individual or a group to achieve a goal in a certain situation" [2].

Summary of the above concepts will see that: Leadership is the process of grasping the correlation of interests between individuals or groups in the organization so that on that basis, the intentional impact will positively affect the members of the organization, of the community to coordinate their potentials, capabilities, and actions towards the common goal. In addition, management is the process of managing subjects impacting on management objects, through the use of certain tools, means, methods and processes, in order to understand the current situation and movement trends of the object, to adjust, motivate the object in the right direction and achieve the overall goal of the organization.

In fact, people in any form of labor who have common goals need leadership and management. Said A. G. Kovaliop, a Russian psychologist: "Implementing goals requires a planned activity, an organic relationship between one member and others in the group. Therefore, there is a need to coordinate everyone's activities with each other and that will be done by a person appointed to lead. Without leadership, it

is impossible to build a community. Even in temporary communities like games, there is a need for a leader" [3].

In that sense, leadership plays an important role in the revolutionary struggle because this is not only a process of activity that changes the quality of all aspects of society, but also activities related to the relationship of rights and interests among social classes. Therefore, without leadership and management, the revolution cannot be done.

Ho Chi Minh is a revolutionary, professional politician of Vietnam. His presence is indispensable in the process of national struggle to survive and develop according to objective laws and the trend of the era. Therefore, Ho Chi Minh's leadership is a political one, with the clear class nature and stance, his management activity is to manage in the political process, a deeply political and social one. As the President of the ruling Party and President of the State for many years - Ho Chi Minh is the leader and the supreme manager of the Vietnamese revolution.

Ho Chi Minh's leadership style is the principles, ways of working as a member, a leader of the Vietnamese ruling Party; being expressed in thinking, expressing, working, behaving and setting an example of revolutionary morality; to awaken and encourage the masses to participate in the revolutionary for the goal of national independence and sustainable development of the country. Along with that, the management style of Ho Chi Minh is the principles, ways of working; formed during the process of carrying out revolutionary activities; to promote the combined strength to realize the goal of national independence associated with freedom, prosperity, and happiness of the people.

Ho Chi Minh's leadership and management style are revolutionary, scientific and humane because Ho Chi Minh's leadership and management goals are directed towards the cause of national liberation, class liberation, and human liberation. The process of exciting practice has formed and built up the leadership and management style of Ho Chi Minh. He not only joined the French Socialist Party; was a founding member of the French Communist Party; was a member of the Communist International; was the founder of the Communist Party of Vietnam, the President of the Communist Party of Vietnam from 1951 until his death, but also participated in founding, managing and working in organizations such as the Colonial Union (1921).); The Eastern Committee of the Communist International (1924); Youth Revolutionary Association of Vietnam and the Association of Oppressed Nations (1925); Institute for the Study of National Affairs and Colonies of the Communist International (1936); Viet Minh Front (1941).

With the leadership and management style as all for the people, taking independence, freedom, prosperity, happiness of the people as a foundation, Ho Chi Minh has always had the right leadership guidelines, the right management decisions which were widely supported by the masses. Specific manifestation is: He has acquired and integrated many ideological essences in political theories of humanity such as Confucianism, Buddhism, Christianity, "Freedom, equality, and humanity" motto of the Western bourgeois revolution and Marxism-Leninism to determine the sustainable development path for the Vietnamese people. It is the path that ensures national independence associated with democracy, peace, freedom, prosperity, happiness of all classes in society. As in the historical Will, he wrote: "My last wish is: The whole Party, our people unite to strive and build a peaceful, united, independent Vietnam, democracy and wealth, and a worthy contribute to the world revolutionary cause" [4].

Regarding the state model, at first, Ho Chi Minh chose the Russian-Soviet model. However, then at the 8th Central Conference (May 1941), the Chairperson adjusted the goal of building a state model to match the interests of the people from all social strata. The conference affirmed: "It is not to say that the union of workers and peasants and the establishment of the Soviet government, but to say the union of the people and the establishment of a republican democratic government" [5]. After the August Revolution 1945, before the famine caused by the colonialists and imperialists, he called for sharing clothes, sharing food; In the cause of resistance war, nationalism, Ho Chi Minh with the Communist Party of Vietnam proposed the way of the people's war, the whole people, comprehensive, long-term, both resistance and national construction so that in the war conditions, people still enjoyed the value of freedom and independence; Immediately after the North was completely liberated, Ho Chi Minh and the Communist Party of Vietnam decided to carry out simultaneously two revolutionary strategies: the Socialist Revolution in the North and the Democratic National Revolution in the South; Before his death, in the Will, he also advised the Party and the State to pay attention to people of all strata such as: exemption of agricultural tax for one year for farmers; take care of war invalids, martyrs' families, people with meritorious services to the revolution, women and especially the young generation.

The leadership and management style of Ho Chi Minh is not only the whole body of activities in the process of realizing thought, creating his own characteristic, but also the style of thought and argument on leadership and management science. Looking at the leadership style and management of Ho Chi Minh City, each of the leaders and managers can draw the principles to train that style for themselves. With the values created - Ho Chi Minh's leadership and management style has developed and enriched the argument about the role of the masses with the leader. The style of the leader or the manager can only be formed in the process of serving the interests of certain ethnic communities, collectives, and organizations. On the other hand, along with strengthening the correctness of the principle of the people as the owners, the people in control and the role of science in the practical

activities of people - the leadership and management style of Ho Chi Minh also contributes to affirm the philosophical role of the consensus between the Party's will and the people's hearts. In fact, the ruling Party can only exist when all policies and guidelines of the Party meet the aspirations and interests of the people and each cadre and party members are truly moral, believed by the people.

Besides the above theoretical values, the leadership and management style of Ho Chi Minh has great practical value. That style has set the standard for a leader of the people, the deep sympathy between a leader and manager with the people. The leadership and management style of Ho Chi Minh is not only a decisive factor in promoting the political party's intelligence and the strength of the entire Vietnamese people for the cause of fighting for national independence and constructing a society in accordance with the development law of mankind, with the trend of the times and aspirations of the masses, but also an important contribution to the cause of fighting for national independence, democracy and Social progress in the world.

Nowadays, the leadership and management style of Ho Chi Minh is still valid and has great significance for the leaders and managers in Vietnam. Besides the development opportunities created by globalization, international integration, and the fourth industrial revolution, the challenges are also getting bigger. Therefore, in order to take advantage of opportunities, overcome challenges, develop quickly and sustainably in the current fierce political competition trend, the requirement is to gather and promote the strength of Human factors, Vietnam's traditional values, potentials, and competitive advantages. However, it depends on the leadership and management style of the subjects, particularly the officials and members of the ruling party in the political system.

Currently, with the results achieved in the construction of the ruling Party, expressed in the rightness and creativity in the guidelines and guidelines of the Party; at the determination of the Central Committee, the Politburo and the Secretariat to fight against corruption and waste; In the drastic management and administration of the Government, it has made an important contribution to strengthening the confidence of the people in all strata for the Party and State. However, there is still a part of cadres and party members who have shown signs of deterioration in political ideology, morality, and lifestyle, negatively affecting the prestige and leadership and management capacity of the Party Committee and government at all levels. This situation shows that the construction and training of leadership and management style of Ho Chi Minh for cadres, party members, especially heads of party and state agencies are deeply political issues.

Building Ho Chi Minh's leadership and management style is the overall activities that make the leadership and management style of the people be properly perceived, constantly spreading and promoting the effectiveness in leadership activities, Party and State management in general, each officer and party member in particular. Accordingly, building the leadership and management style of Ho Chi Minh for the leaders and managers in Vietnam today is a deliberate

impact process, in order to make the leadership and management style of Ho Chi Minh not only penetrates into the personality of each individual leader and manager at all levels but also must be expressed in the views, guidelines, lines, resolutions, policies, and laws, specific administrative laws and decisions. This goal requires good implementation of some of the following measures:

Firstly, continue to improve the quality and effectiveness of implementing Directive 05 of the Politburo, the XII course on promoting learning and following Ho Chi Minh's ideology, morality and style. In the coming time, it is necessary to study in depth to clarify the characteristics and nature of Ho Chi Minh's working style in general, his leadership and management style in particular. On that basis, it affirms the historical value and great practical significance of Ho Chi Minh's leadership and management style for the Vietnamese revolution and for each current cadre and party member. Actively innovating and creating many rich forms, in accordance with the responsibilities, tasks and professional work of each agency and unit to propagate and educate ideology, morality and Ho Chi style Minh. It is necessary to combine propaganda and education to raise awareness for cadres, party members and people about Ho Chi Minh style with increasing struggle, criticizing opinions, acts of distorting and denying Ho Chi Minh's style, especially his leadership and management style. Through the implementation of Directive 05 of the Politburo, course XII, each cadre, party member, first of all the leaders and managers must understand deeply about the way of formation, nature, and characteristics of Ho Chi Minh's leadership and management style and know how to apply creatively into their own field of work.

Secondly, build and perfect standards of style for leaders and managers at all levels. The leadership and management activities have many different levels and scope, while the leadership and management activities of Ho Chi Minh are mentioned at the macro and the highest level of the nation. Even so, every leader and manager at all levels can learn and follow. That style has become a theory of philosophy and truth about leadership and management. However, on the basis of Ho Chi Minh's style, each subject should base himself on the characteristics, requirements, and tasks of his level to build and perfect the standards of leadership style and management for suitable for each specific title. The construction and improvement of standards are not only a basis for each leader and manager to actively train, but also a basis for competent authorities to quantify and evaluate the learning effectiveness, follow by officials.

Thirdly, highlighting the role and responsibility of the party committees and leaders in implementing the cadre work process, closely combining the leadership style with management style. Personnel work, including leading officials and managers, is the work of Party committees and heads of all levels. Therefore, the committees and heads of all levels have a decisive role in the quality and effectiveness of the stages and steps in the cadre work process. Accordingly, in conducting cadre work in general, building leadership and management styles for officials in particular, requiring the executive committee at all levels to really promote

responsibility, conscience, objectivity, profit collective benefits of the organization as a basis for selection, training, retraining, promotion, appointment and management and use of officials. Leadership and management activities have general requirements and close relationships. Especially in the context of the ruling Party like in Vietnam, the majority of management officials in the administrative apparatus are party members, at the same time implementing both leadership and management functions. Therefore, training leadership style should closely combine with the training management style of cadres and party members.

Fourthly, continue to innovate the content, forms, and methods of assessing the quality of cadres and party members, especially leaders and managers. Assessing the quality of cadres is the most important stage of the working process, judging correctly is the basis to decide on the correctness of the remaining stages. Therefore, it is necessary to continue to innovate the content, forms, and methods of assessing the quality of officials, especially leaders and managers at all levels. Accordingly, to appreciate the right staff must thoroughly grasp the viewpoint of comprehensive, historical, specific and development. Ho Chi Minh stressed: "Considering officials, not only look at the face but also see their nature. Not just watching one thing, at a time, but having to see all their history, their whole work. Someone at the high revolutionary movement, they entered the Party, they worked very hard. But when the movement was a bit difficult, it went into confusion. At the time of the danger even turned against the revolution, as a spy. Want to be a good spy, you need to work harder than anyone else. If we don't consider it clearly, it's wrong to be a good officer" [6]. Therefore, on the one hand, it is necessary to uphold the fairness and objectivity of the collective committee, on the other hand, it should be based on specific criteria, especially the standards of style, built on the basis of Ho Chi Minh's leadership and management style to evaluate. Along with that, in assessing cadres, especially management leaders, it is necessary to base on the results of completing tasks and the trust of agencies and units under the authority, the trust of agencies Relevant and especially of the leaders and managers.

Fifth, promote the role of the people and mass organizations in checking, monitoring and evaluating the style of leaders and managers at the same level. Leadership and management, especially in the political field, do not play a role in themselves; if they separate from the public, that activity is no longer meaningful. Ensuring the rights and legitimate interests of the people is the basis for the birth and existence of leadership and management activities. Therefore, in the inspection, supervision, and evaluation of management leadership style and learning outcomes, following Ho Chi Minh's leadership and management style, cadres need to promote the role of the people where the cadres reside and live and the role of mass organizations - the place directly under the influence and influence of that leadership style. According to Ho Chi Minh, "People who are in close contact with the people, know the people. Always pay attention to the interests of the people. Thus, the new people trust their officials and accept them as their leaders" [7].

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